

**Music therapy research through the eye of Medical Science in
cardiovascular disorders (CVD) and coronary care**

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Abstract

*Today«s hectic life style, working stress & tension creating various types of health problems such unusual B.P., Cardiovascular problems, headache, psychological disorders, depression, sleeplessness, nervous problems etc. which are sometime converted in to serious problems and effecting the family life & working efficiency of the person. Now a days in place to fight these problems most of us and teenagers are starting use of alcohol, smoking and other unhealthy things to overcome the stress, tension, depression but they are helpful for time being and become emerged itself as a new problem. Music therapy is a way by which aforesaid problems can easily control. Research conducted in the field of bio-musicology explains that music therapy is helpful in controlling B.P., angina, labour pain, impotency, Indigestion, Hypertension, to build confidence, insomnia, Anxiety, Depression, Headache, Hyperacidity, Sleep disorders, if used in scientific way by demarking it from sound pollution. It can also very helpful in controlling pre and post operative stress and improvement of child behaviour. Music therapy mostly target on various neuro-endocrine functions of body to cure various type of disorder. **Music therapy** is an allied health profession and a field of scientific research which studies correlations between the process of clinical therapy and bio-musicology. It is an interpersonal process in which a music therapist uses music and all of its facets physical, emotional, mental, social, aesthetic, and spiritual to help clients to improve or maintain their health.*

Indian classical ‘Ragas’ have been acclaimed by Vedic science to have healing effects. Music has frequently been used as a therapeutic agent from the ancient times. Music acts upon the human organism and awakens and develops their proper functions to the extent of self-realization, which is the ultimate goal of all religious Philosophy.

Music therapy is also widely reported in the medical literature together with historical and mythological literature. This paper helps the music therapist and bio-musicologist in the establishment of research strategies for supporting clinical practice.

Key Words: CVD, Coronary care, Music Therapy, Bio-musicology.

Introduction

Music therapy is using since time immemorial and It is an established fact that brain is controlling entire metabolism of the body through different mechanisms and if any mechanism disturbed by any agents (antigens) it reflects in form of disease or disorder. Sound vibrations in form of music can influence the brain and be able to control the unhealthy stage of body. Music therapy has risen to the challenge of research in recent years. Not only is there a tradition of quantitative research but qualitative research approaches have been also incorporated within the discipline as is necessary for an clinical

approach that involves science and art (Aldridge 1996; Dileo 1999; Pratt and Spintge 1996; Pratt and Erdonmez-Grocke 1999).

Music can make you laugh or cry, rile you up or calm you down. Some say it's good for the soul. It might be good for the heart, too as researchers have turned their attention to the effects of music on the cardiovascular system, they have found that listening to music can lower blood pressure, slow the heart rate, and lessen anxiety in people hospitalized for heart ailments. It can ease pain and distress after cardiac surgery. In otherwise healthy people, music can lower blood pressure and ease stress. Today, music therapy is most commonly used for people undergoing a cardiac procedure and for those recovering from a heart attack or learning to cope with heart failure or another cardiovascular condition, like angina or heart failure. For them, music therapy can alleviate stress, provide a pleasant coping strategy, and impart a feeling of control.

*Research findings suggest that the **music** can also stimulate the body to produce the molecule nitric oxide (NO). nitric oxide works on the tonus of blood vessels which can reduce blood pressure. Music also found to decrease cortisol and increasing adrenalin and endorphins level in body.*

After the world war- second music therapy was intensively developed in American hospitals. Since then some hospitals, particularly in mainland Europe, have incorporated music therapy within their practice carrying on a tradition of European hospital based research and practice. The nursing profession has seen the value of music therapy, particularly in the United States of America, and championed its use as an important nursing intervention even when music therapists are not available. Indeed, it is a clinical nurse specialist has made an overview of fourteen articles on audioanalgesia (Bechler-Karsch 1993). She reports a confusing picture of changes related to heart rate but a clearer picture emerges on physiological parameters related to pain and anxiety and she concludes that music has no adverse effects on ill patients when used as an adjunctive non-invasive therapy. Standley (1986,1995) has consistently reviewed the literature relating to music therapy applications in medical settings made a meta-analysis of the current findings from 55 studies utilizing 129 dependent variables (Standley 1995). Standley concludes that the average therapeutic effect of music in medical treatment is almost one standard deviation greater than without music (.88). From these results she generalizes that women react more favourably to music than men, as do children compared with adults. While music is less effective for severe pain it is indicated for chronic pain. Live music administered by a music therapist has a greater effect than recorded music and the effect sizes vary according to the dependent measure being used, physiological measures being stronger than subjective assessment.

During the last 1990's there has been a collection of writings related to the clinical application of music therapy, often from symposia (Pratt and Erdonmez-Grocke 1999; Pratt and Spintge 1996), and the development of research strategies suitable to clinical application (Aldridge 1996; Wheeler 1995).

Impact of Music therapy on heart rate and respiration

The effect of music on the cardiovascular disorders (CVD) been a favourite theme throughout history. This is initially evident in "Lancet" (medical journal), In which Vincent and Thompson (1929) made an attempt to discover the influence of listening to gramophone, and radio, music on blood pressure and he observed that listening to music was accompanied by a slight rise in blood pressure in the listener. If music produces physiological and psychological effects, in healthy persons as listeners then it may be assumed that persons with various diseases respond to music in specific

ways, hence music can be used therapeutically for patients who have problems with heart disease or hypertension. Bason and Celler (1972) observed that the human heart rate could be varied over a certain range by entrainment of the sinus rhythm with external auditory stimulus which presumably acted through the nervous control mechanisms, and resulted from a neural coupling into the cardiac centers of the brain. An audible click was played to the subject at a precise time in the cardiac cycle. When it came within a critical range then the heart rate could be increased or decreased up to 12% over a period of time up to 3 minutes. Fluctuations caused by breathing remained, but these tended to be less when the heart was entrained with the audible stimulus. When the click was not within the time range of the cardiac cycle then no influence could be made. Bason's paper is important for supporting the proposition often made by music therapists that meeting the tempo of the patient influences their musical playing and is the initial key to therapeutic change.

An extension of this premise, that musical rhythm is a pacemaker, was investigated by Haas *et al.* (1986) in terms of the effects of perceived rhythm on respiratory pattern, a pattern that serves both metabolic and behavioural functions. Metabolic respiratory pathways are located in the reticular formation of the lower pons and medulla, whereas the behavioral respiratory pathways are located mainly in the limbic forebrain structures that lead to vocalization and complex behavior. There appear to be both hypothalamic and spinal pattern generators capable of synchronizing this respiratory and locomotor activity. Therefore, Haas hypothesized that an external rhythmical musical activity, in this case listening to taped music, would have an influence on respiratory pattern while keeping metabolic changes and afferent stimuli (i.e. no gross motor movements) to a minimum. In this experiment twenty subjects were involved, out of them four of whom were experienced musicians and practicing musicians, six had formal musical training but no longer played a musical instrument and the remaining ten had no musical training. Respiratory data including respiration frequency and airflow volume was collected alongside heart rate and end-tidal CO₂. Subjects listened to a metronome set at 60b.p.m. and tapped to that beat on a microphone after a baseline period. The subjects were then randomly presented with four musical excerpts and a period of silence with which they tapped along to. There were no appreciable changes in heart rate during the experiment, but there was an appreciable change in respiratory frequency and a significant decrease in the coefficient of variation for all respiratory parameters during the finger tapping. For non-musically trained subjects there was little coordination between breathing and musical rhythm, while for trained musicians there was a coupling of breathing and rhythm. That singers have more efficient pulmonary strategies than non-trained musicians, even when talking, is supported elsewhere in the literature (Formby *et al.* 1989). Auditory cues, then, appear to be important in the synchronization of respiration and other motor activity. It is this aspect of organization of behavioral events that appears to be the important aspect of music and central to music therapy (Aldridge 2000).

Several authors have investigated this relationship in the setting of hospital care (Bonny 1983; Davis *et al.* 1987; Zimmerman *et al.* 1988; Guzzetta 1989; Philip 1989; Elliott 1994) often with the intent of reducing anxiety in chronically ill patients (Gross and Swartz 1982; Standley 1986), for treating anxiety in general (Robb 2000), or specifically in musicians (Brodsky and Sloboda 1997).

A hospital situation that is fraught with anxiety for the patient is the intensive care unit. For patients after a heart attack, where heart rhythms are potentially unstable, the setting of coronary care is itself anxiety provoking which recursively influences the physiological and psychological reactions of the patient. In these situations several authors, in varying hospital intensive care or coronary care clinics, have assessed the use of tape recorded music delivered through headphones as an anxiolytic with the intention of reducing stress (Updike 1990). Bonny (1978, 1983) has suggested

a series of musical selections for tape recordings which can be chosen for their sedative effects and according to other mood criteria, associative imagery and relaxation potential, none of which have been empirically confirmed. For this Updike (1990) conducted an experiment and confirms Bonny's impression that there is a decreased systolic blood pressure, and a beneficial mood change from anxiety to relaxed calm, when sedative music is played.

*Rider (1985a,b) explained that disease related stress was caused by the desynchronization of circadian oscillators and that listening to sedative music, with a guided imagery induction, would promote the entrainment of circadian rhythms as expressed in temperature and corticosteroid levels of nursing staff. This study found no conclusive results, mainly because there was no control group. Davis-Rollans and Cunningham (1987) describes the use of a 37-minute tape recording of selected classical music (Beethoven *Symphony Nr.6* -first movement; Mozart, *Eine kleine Nachtmusik* -first and fourth movements and Smetana, *The Moldau*) on the heart rate and rhythm of coronary care unit patients. Twelve of the patients had had heart attacks and another twelve had a chronic heart condition. Patients were exposed to two randomly varied 42-minute periods of continuous monitoring; one period with music delivered through headphones, the other control period was without music and contained background noise of the unit as heard through silent headphones. Eight patients reported a significant change to a happier emotional state after listening to the music (a result replicated by Updike,1990), although there were no significant changes in specific physiological variables during the music periods. Music relieves depression, is believed to be beneficial to the overall status of coronary care patients (Cassem and Hackett 1971).*

*Bolwerk (1990) set out to relieve the state anxiety of patients in a myocardial infarction ward using recorded classical music (Bach, *Largo*; Beethoven, *Largo*; Debussy, *Prelude to the Afternoon of a Faun*). Forty adults were randomly assigned to two equal groups; one of which listened to relaxing music during the first four days of hospitalization, the other received no music. There was no controlled "silent condition". While there was a significant reduction in state anxiety in the treatment group, state anxiety was also reduced in the control group. The reasons for this overall reduction in anxiety may have been that after four days the situation had become less acute, the situation was not so strange for the patient, and by then a diagnosis had been confirmed. State anxiety is an individual's anxiety at a particular state in time, as opposed to trait anxiety that is an overall prevailing condition of anxiety unbounded by time and determined by personality. The relationship between stress and anxiety is that stimulus conditions, or stressors, produce anxiety reactions; i.e. the state of anxiety. Anxiety as a state is characterized by subjective feelings of tension, worry and nervousness which are accompanied by physiological changes of heart rate, blood pressure, myocardial oxygen consumption, lethal cardiac dysrhythmias and reductions in peripheral and renal perfusion. Admission to the coronary care unit is itself a stressor, and the environment produces further stress, therefore the importance for managing state anxiety.*

Guzzetta (1989) conducted a study to determine whether relaxation and music therapy were effective in reducing stress in patients admitted to a coronary care unit with the presumptive diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction. In this experimental study, 80 patients were randomly assigned to a relaxation, music therapy, or control group. The relaxation and music therapy groups participated in three sessions over a two-day period. Music therapy was comprised of a relaxation induction and listening to a 20 minute musical cassette tape selected from three alternative musical styles; soothing classical music, soothing popular music and non-traditional music. Stress was evaluated by apical heart rates, peripheral temperatures, cardiac complications, and qualitative patient evaluative data. Data analysis revealed that lowering apical heart rates and raising peripheral temperatures were more

successful in the relaxation and music therapy groups than in the control group. The incidence of cardiac complications was found to be lower in the intervention groups, and most intervention subjects believed that such therapy was helpful. Both relaxation and music therapy were found to be effective modalities of reducing stress in these patients, and music listening was more effective than relaxation alone. Furthermore, apical heart rates were lowered in response to music over a series of sessions thus supporting the argument that the assessment of music therapy on physiological parameters is dependent upon adaptation over time. Further research strategies may wish to make longitudinal studies of the influence of music on physiological parameters.

Above positive finding of Guzzetta (1989) was in contrast to Zimmerman et al. (1988) who failed to find an influence of music on heart rate, peripheral temperature, blood pressure or anxiety score. However, Zimmerman's study only allowed for one intervention of music. In this experimental study the authors examined the effects of listening to relaxation-type music on self-reported anxiety and on selected physiologic indices of relaxation in patients with suspected myocardial infarction. Seventy-five patients were randomly assigned to one of two experimental groups, one listening to taped music and the other to "white noise" ("White noise" or "synthetic silence" is an attempt to block out environmental noise. In this case it was a tape recording of sea sounds, which themselves were rhythmic) through headphones, or to a control group. The Spielberger State Anxiety Inventory (Spielberger, 1983) was administered before and after each testing session, and blood pressure, heart rate, and digital skin temperature were measured at baseline and at 10-minute intervals for the 30-minute session. There was no significant difference among the three groups for state anxiety scores or physiologic parameters. Because no differences were found, analyses were conducted of the groups combined. Significant improvement in all of the physiologic parameters was found to have occurred. This finding reinforces the benefit of rest and careful monitoring of patients in the coronary care unit, but adds little to the understanding of music interventions. Time to listen, separated from the surrounding influence of the hospital unit by the use of headphones, may itself be an important intervention. Although Rider (1985a) did not reach this preceding conclusion; he found that perceived pain was reduced in a hospital situation in response to classical music delivered through headphones, it could be concluded from his work that isolation from environmental sounds, canceling out external noise, has a positive benefit for the patient regardless of inner content, i.e. music, relaxation induction or silence. Given that Bason's (1972) study could influence heart rate by matching the heart rate of the patient, then we must conclude that studies of the influence of music on heart rate must match the music to the individual patient. This also makes psychological sense as different people have varied reactions to the same music. Furthermore, improvised music playing which takes meeting the tempo of the patient as one of its main principles may have an impact other than the passive listening to music. In addition, the work of Haas (Haas et al. 1986) mentioned above showed that listening, coupled with tapping, synchronizes respiration pattern with musical rhythm, further emphasizing that active music playing can be used to influence physiological parameters and that this synchronization can be learned.

Conclusion

Now a day's ample literature are available covering the application of music therapy as reported in the medical press and a growing resource of valid clinical research material from which substantive conclusions can be drawn. Most of the work conducted in cardiovascular disorder are related with coronary care, but there attempt is forwarding steps to use music as therapeutic tools. Still more attempts are required to prove music as drug for various type of CVD and in coronary care. But no one can denied the fact that aforesaid work laid the foundation stone for a future in

which music will be used as Complimentary and alternate medicine (CAM) without any doubt.

We can't say that all music therapy clinical research should conform to a common methodology or that it be medical research, rather than standard research tools and methods of clinical assessment be developed which can be replicated, which are appropriate to music therapy, and develop a link with other forms of clinical practice. In this way we develop working tools which allow us to inform others and ourselves. Much of the research work has been developed within the field of CVD and coronary care where the use of music is accepted as a useful therapeutic adjunct. Not surprisingly, the work from this field has concentrated on medical scientific perspectives. There is almost a complete absence of cross-cultural studies, or the use of anthropological methods that would bring other insights into music therapy. That music has been used therapeutically in other cultures cannot be denied, and other perspectives regarding the application of music therapeutically would highlight the limitations of modern Western scientific approaches when used as the sole means of research.

Most of the scientific work conducted in the field of music therapy was related with foreign environment. India is the land of music, in various tribal's music is used as a tool to treat disorders, but it is disjuncting that our government and hospitals are not taking it seriously. Music therapy still needs its identification by government of India. Our recommendation to our government is that they should include music therapy and Bio-musicology as part naturopathy and promotes its scientific research as a innovative field in various educational and scientific bodies or establish a Indian council of Bio-musical research like ICMR, so we can also use music therapy not only in cardiovascular and coronary care but also in other field of health science and as result of this it can be use as CAM without any confusion in our country.

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